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Из всего вышеуказанного можно сделать вывод, что миграция имеет не только отрицательный эффект, но и много положительных моментов. Нельзя оценивать миграцию отрицательно, в частности, трудовую.

Государству посредством миграционной политики необходимо решать такие проблемы как: сокращение безработицы, создание благоприятных условий для возвращения образованных людей, регулирование «качества» иностранной рабочей силы и др. Федеральная миграционная служба может давать эфиры с объяснением значимости миграции для местного населения, чтобы избежать напряженности в обществе и избавиться от стереотипов, что миграция - это плохо и русские живут только в России. Также взаимодействие между собой стран и в целом мирового сообщества в миграционной политике в дальнейшем может привести к сокращению негативных факторов.

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Using the Assessment Center tools for diagnostics managerial and professional competencies of personnel

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Abstract

This article substantiates the possibilities of using the Assessment Center tools for diagnosing the managerial and professional competencies of personnel and the formation of human capital of an enterprise. In modern conditions, personnel represent the basis of the human capital of an enterprise. In this regard, approaches to increasing his managerial and professional competencies are becoming increasingly relevant. The purpose of this study is to analyze the functionality and tools of the Assessment Center method for diagnosing managerial and professional competencies. The personnel selected were mid-level managers from one of the enterprises in the most dynamically developing sector of the economy - the development, implementation and development of digital economy products. To conduct an empirical study, the tools of the Assessment Center were selected, as well as methods of qualitative and quantitative analysis of managerial and professional competencies of managers. This apparatus made it possible to determine the importance of managerial and professional competencies in the formation of human capital of enterprises and to implement in practice a dynamic approach to assessing their level. The results obtained during the study make it possible to implement a group or individual approach to training enterprise personnel and developing the necessary managerial and professional competencies.

Keywords: enterprise, personnel, human capital, managerial and professional competencies, formation.

Аннотация

В данной статье обоснованы возможности использования инструментария Ассесмент центра для диагностики управленческих и профессиональных компетенций персонала и формирования человеческого капитала предприятия. В современных условиях персонал представляет основу человеческого капитала предприятия. В этой связи повышенную актуальность приобретают подходы к росту его управленческих и профессиональных компетенций. Целью данного исследования является анализ функциональных возможностей и инструментария метода Ассесмент центра для диагностики управленческих и профессиональных компетенций. В качестве персонала были выбраны менеджеры среднего звена управления одного из предприятий наиболее динамично развивающейся сферы экономики - разработки, внедрения и развития продуктов цифровой экономики. Для проведения эмпирического исследования был выбран инструментарий Ассесмент центра, а также методы качественного и количественного анализа управленческих и профессиональных компетенций менеджеров. Этот аппарат позволил определить значение управленческих и профессиональных компетенций в формировании человеческого капитала предприятий и реализовать на практике динамический подход к оценке их уровня. Полученные в ходе исследования результаты позволяют реализовать групповой или индивидуальный подход к обучению персонала предприятий и развитию у него необходимых управленческих и профессиональных компетенций.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, персонал, человеческий капитал, управленческие и профессиональные компетенции, формирование.

Introduction

The implementation of sanctions restrictions had a negative impact on the production and economic activities of many Russian enterprises. Therefore, in modern conditions, promising directions and opportunities for their progressive development are largely determined by the high level of managerial and professional competencies of personnel. They play a decisive role in the formation of human capital of enterprises. The industry affiliation of each enterprise and a number of other key factors of its production and economic activity presuppose the need to individualize approaches to the formation of human capital of each enterprise.

The development of human capital of enterprises is especially important for minimizing the negative impact of sanctions restrictions. It is based on achieving optimal correspondence between the development of management competencies of the management level of the enterprise (managers at the top, middle and lower levels of management) and the professional competencies of specialists at various levels involved in the production of products. Naturally, the managerial and professional competencies of enterprise personnel are constantly changing over time. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to ensure an optimal balance between them, depending on the profile of the enterprise's production and economic activities, its industry affiliation and a number of other key factors.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to analyze the functionality and tools of the Assessment Center (AC) method, as well as methods of qualitative and quantitative analysis for diagnosing the managerial and professional competencies of enterprise personnel.

Materials and research methods

To achieve this goal, the six most significant managerial and professional competencies of middle-level managers were selected from the point of view of their influence on the performance of each manager and the enterprise as a whole. They included: result orientation, leadership, performance

management, ability to work in a team, stress resistance, self-organization. AC tools [1, 2], as well as methods of qualitative and quantitative analysis, were used as methodological support for the research and assessment of management competencies.

The assessment center is one of the most objective methods used to assess professional and managerial competencies [4, 5]. Its objectivity is ensured by the use of various tools (business games, cases, interviews, basketball method, etc.), clearly defined behavioral indicators, and the involvement of experts who have undergone special training [6]. The works of many Russian and foreign scientists are devoted to describing the theory and practice of using the AC methodology and tools [1, 3, 7, 8]. In their works, they substantiate the feasibility of its use for a variety of purposes, one way or another related to the assessment of professional and managerial competencies of enterprise personnel [3, 9].

To assess the management competencies of middle managers of the enterprise, a three-point scale with a step equal to "0.25" points was chosen. The study sample consisted of 12 middle managers of the enterprise (heads of departments), whose age ranged from 24 to 47 years. Among them were 9 men and 3 women.

The process of assessing the management competencies of middle managers of an enterprise using the AC method was carried out using standard technology and contained all the prescribed stages [1, 3, 5]. The results of the qualitative and quantitative analysis of management competencies are given below.

Results and discussion

The final scores for each competency and for the totality of competencies for each of the 12 middle managers are given below (see Table 1).

Table 1

Summary table with final assessments of the competencies of each manager.

No p/p	Evaluation criterion (competence)	Participants											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	Result oriented	1,25	2,25	2,0	1,75	2,0	1,75	2,0	2,0	1,5	1,75	0,5	2,0
2	Leadership	0,75	1,5	1,5	2,0	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,75	1,0	1,25	1,0	1,25
3	Execution Management	1,0	2,0	1,25	1,75	1,5	1,75	1,5	2,0	1,5	1,25	1,75	1,25
4	Skill to work in team	1,5	1,0	1,75	1,75	1,5	1,25	1,75	1,75	1,5	2,0	2,25	1,75
5	Stress resistance	1,75	1,5	1,75	2,0	1,75	1,75	1,5	1,5	1,5	2,0	1,0	2,0
6	Self-organization	1,5	1,5	1,5	2,0	1,5	1,5	1,5	2,0	2,0	1,75	1,75	1,75
Final assessment of competencies		1,3	1,6	1,6	1,9	1,6	1,6	1,6	1,8	1,5	1,6	1,4	1,7

To illustrate the qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data in Table 1, graphs for presenting assessments for each of the studied management competencies were used. Thus, Chart 1 shows assessments of the managerial competence "Result Orientation", which show that the majority of middle managers of the enterprise have a level of this competence that should be considered above average (1.75 \square 2.0). It is understood by all managers and is actively applied by them in practice. From this we can conclude that the majority of middle managers clearly understand the tasks assigned to them, are focused on achieving results, and make certain efforts to implement the planned tasks. Many people tend to be flexible in finding solutions. Noteworthy are the similar overall values for this competency of the following groups of managers: No. 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 12 (2.25; 2.0; 2.0; 2.0; 2.0; 2, 0 respectively); No. 4, 6, 9, 10 (1.75; 1.75; 1.5; 1.75, respectively). The ratings of this managerial competence from managers No. 1 and No. 11 (1.25 and 0.5 points, respectively) stand out from the overall picture for the worse.

Figure 1. Summary data for the "Results Orientation" competency. Assessments of the management competency "Leadership" are presented in Chart 2.

Figure 2. Summary data for the Leadership competency.

It clearly shows that for the majority of middle managers they are in the development zone and are generally the weakest competency in the sample under study. Most of the managers assessed, with few exceptions, do not seek to occupy a leadership position in the group, preferring the roles of observer and performer, or seek to transfer this function to a stronger leader. In communications, managers usually display a partnership style of communication, both among themselves and in situations of interaction with subordinates, which, obviously, is part of the company's corporate culture.

For this competency, the following groups of managers with similar scores are distinguished: No. 1, 9, 11 (0.75; 1.0; 1.0, respectively); No. 2, 3, 5, 6, 7 (1.5; 1.5, 1.5; 1.5; 1.5, respectively).

Assessments of the management competency "Execution Management" are presented in Chart 3.

Figure 3. Summary of data on the "Execution Management" competency.

The graph shows that most managers are at an average or above average level of development. Consequently, they generally understand and practice this management competency. They are able to assign tasks to subordinates and evaluate the results of their work. Some managers know about the need and importance of delegating their powers, but, as a rule, they do it intuitively, not always

understanding which functions can be delegated to others. Such an important function of a manager as control also requires special attention. Unfortunately, the vast majority of managers have demonstrated a lack of skills in intermediate control of the work of subordinates.

For this competency, the following groups of managers with similar scores are distinguished: No. 2, 4, 6, 8, 11 (2.0; 1.75; 1.75; 2.0; 1.75, respectively); No. 1, 3, 10, 12 (1.0; 1.25; 1.25; 1.25, respectively).

Assessments of the managerial competence “Ability to work in a team” are presented in Graph 4. The graph shows that this competence is at a fairly good level of development. The middle managers who participated in its assessment showed an interest in solving team-wide problems, effective and efficient team interaction, the ability to create a comfortable working atmosphere in the team and a willingness to contribute to the development of this management competency. Individual managers have the skills to motivate subordinates.

Figure 4. Summary data on the “Ability to work in a team” competency.

For this competency, the following groups of managers with similar scores are distinguished: No. 2, 6 (1.0; 1.25, respectively); No. 3, 4, 7, 8, 12 (1.75; 1.75; 1.75; 1.75; 1.75, respectively); No. 1, 5, 9 (1.5; 1.5; 1.5, respectively); No. 10, 11 (2.0; 2.25, respectively).

Assessments of the managerial competence “Stress resistance” are presented in Graph 5. The graph shows that this competence is at an average level of development. During its assessment, managers showed the ability to keep their emotions under control, respond adequately to an unfriendly attitude, remain calm, work effectively in stressful situations and quickly recover from them, as well as high performance under long-term workloads with a large amount of information.

Figure 5. Summary data on the “Stress Resistance” competency.

For this competency, the following groups of managers with similar scores are distinguished: No. 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 12 (1.75; 1.75; 1.75; 1.75; 2.0; 2.0 respectively); No. 2, 7, 8, 9 (1.5; 1.5; 1.5; 1.5, respectively); No. 11 stands apart (1.0 point exactly).

Assessments of the managerial competence “Self-organization” are presented in Graph 6.

Figure 6. Summary data on the “Self-organization” competency.

The graph shows that this competence is demonstrated at an average level. Managers in general know how to plan their actions over time, rationally set priorities, although they do not always do this effectively, they confuse the concept of urgency and importance of tasks, most managers prefer to see and track strict deadlines, some know how to organize things during the day harmoniously and efficiently, group them in order of importance, but only a small part. Almost all managers understand the importance of managing such a resource as tracking time within a business task during its implementation, but do not actually track it; During the AC process, timing units were observed only by individual managers.

For this competency, the following groups of managers with similar ratings are distinguished: No. 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7 (1.5; 1.5; 1.5; 1.5; 1.5, respectively); No. 4, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 (2.0; 2.0; 2.0; 1.75; 1.75; 1.75, respectively).

In general, in the obtained results of assessing a number of competencies of the studied sample of middle managers, the following circumstances attract attention:

1) the absence of scores above 2.25 points for any competency, which indicates the degree of development of competencies only at the level of experience, when competency is manifested in standard situations, therefore, the manifestation of competencies in non-standard, creative situations requiring initiative is not typical for the sample under study ;

2) the possibility of identifying groups according to the level of development of competencies, which makes it possible to structure the sample in terms of developing training programs for the development of those competencies that are not yet sufficiently developed in the sample under study.

Before conducting correlation analysis, the obtained assessments of management competencies were compared with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normal distribution. Since in our case the distribution turned out to be non-normal, it was decided to use the nonparametric Spearman test.

Below is a table of correlations between all competency variables (see Table 2).

Table 2

Correlations between all competency variables.

			<i>Result oriented</i>	<i>Leadership</i>	<i>Execution Management</i>	<i>Skill to work in team</i>	<i>Stress resistance</i>	<i>Self-organization</i>
<i>Spearman's rho</i>	<i>Result oriented</i>	<i>Correlation coefficient</i>		0.601	0.228	-0.260	0.046	-0.309
		<i>Meaning (double-sided)</i>		0.039	0.476	0.415	0.888	0.328
		<i>No.</i>		12	12	12	12	12
	<i>Leadership</i>	<i>Correlation coefficient</i>			0.574	-0.072	0.131	0.071
		<i>Meaning (double-sided)</i>			0.051	0.823	0.684	0.826
		<i>No.</i>			12	12	12	12
	<i>Execution Management</i>	<i>Correlation coefficient</i>				-0.183	-0.509	0.250
		<i>Meaning (double-sided)</i>				0.569	0.091	0.432
		<i>No.</i>				12	12	12
	<i>Skill to work in</i>	<i>Correlation coefficient</i>					0.080	0.440

team	Meaning (double-sided)							0.804	0.152
	No.							12	12
Stress resistance	Correlation coefficient								0.036
	Meaning (double-sided)								0.912
	No.								12

When analyzing the correlation matrix of the answers given by the respondents, an average positive relationship was identified between the “Result Orientation” and “Leadership” competencies (0.601). It is due to the fact that both competencies have a proactive component, since each of them implies the manager’s activity in achieving the goal. A positive relationship was also found between the “Leadership” and “Execution Management” competencies (0.574). Its presence can be interpreted in this way: both competencies are related to personnel management and are acquired by managers during this process. Accordingly, it can be assumed that a manager who pays more attention to leading others and growing his professionalism developed both competencies simultaneously.

Noteworthy is the identification of an average negative relationship between the management competencies “Stress Resistance” and “Performance Management” (-0.509). This may be due to the fact that more stress-resistant managers are able to work with more information and tasks and have less need to delegate tasks to others (the latter is related to the “Execution Management” competency). At the same time, less stress-resistant managers tend to delegate more tasks to other performers in order to “unload” themselves and reduce the influence of stress factors, such as multitasking and the need to work with large amounts of information.

In order to obtain grounds for the formation of training groups for the subsequent development of managers' competencies, a correlation analysis of assessments for all competencies between them was carried out. As a result, the following connections were identified:

- a high positive relationship between managers No. 1 and 10 (0.924) (correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 (two-sided)), as well as between managers No. 10 and 12 (0.886) (correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 (two-sided));

- average positive relationship between managers No. 1 and 12 (0.828) (correlation significant at the level of 0.05 (two-sided)), between managers No. 2 and 6 (0.833) (correlation significant at the level of 0.05 (two-sided)), between managers No. 3 and 7 (0.798) (correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-sided)); between managers No. 3 and 12 (0.835) (correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed)).

For optimal planning of activities for the development of managerial competencies, it is possible to unite managers into groups based on the principle of similarity of the results they obtained. To do this, you can use the results of qualitative and quantitative analysis of the obtained assessments of their competencies (see Tables 2 and 3).

Table 3

Identifying the relationship between the “Managers” variables

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	Pearson correlation		-0.347	0.453	0.124	0.243	-0.055	0.081	-0.388	0.644	0.924	0.184	0.828
	Value (two-way)		0.445	0.308	0.790	0.600	0.907	0.864	0.390	0.118	0.003	0.693	0.021
2	Pearson correlation			0.055	-0.312	0.611	0.833	0.340	0.557	0.000	-0.412	-0.636	-0.001
	Value (two-way)			0.907	0.496	0.145	0.020	0.455	0.194	1.000	0.358	0.124	0.998
3	Pearson correlation				-0.176	0.798	-0.001	0.798	-0.230	0.000	0.698	-0.479	0.835
	Value (two-way)				0.705	0.031	0.998	0.031	0.620	1.000	0.081	0.277	0.020
4	Pearson correlation					-0.221	0.003	-0.656	-0.450	0.000	-0.006	-0.210	0.003

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Value (two-way)					0.634	0.996	0.110	0.311	1.000	0.990	0.652	0.995
5	Pearson correlation						0.583	0.715	0.003	0.000	0.352	-0.785	0.696
	Value (two-way)						0.170	0,071	0.994	1.000	0.438	0.037	0.082
6	Pearson correlation							-0.002	0.097	0.000	-0.241	-0.661	0.121
	Value (two-way)							0.997	0.835	1.000	0.603	0.106	0.797
7	Pearson correlation								0.295	0.000	0.352	-0.324	0.522
	Value (two-way)								0.521	1.000	0.438	0.479	0.230
8	Pearson correlation									0.386	-0.411	0.093	-0.241
	Value (two-way)									0.392	0.360	0.842	0.603
9	Pearson correlation										0.461	0.366	0.463
	Value (two-way)										0.297	0.419	0.296
10	Pearson correlation											0.111	0.886
	Value (two-way)											0.812	0.008
11	Pearson correlation												-0.282
	Value (two-way)												0.540

Based on these results, the following groups were formed: group 1, in which it is advisable to include managers No. 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 10, 12; group 2, in which it is advisable to include managers No. 2 and 6. For managers No. 8, 11 and 4, no connections were identified in the correlation matrix.

To visualize the data, individual graphs of the profiles of management competencies of managers No. 8, 11 and 4 were constructed (graphs No. 7, 8, 9, respectively).

Figure 7. Individual competency profile of a manager at No. 8.

As we see, in the individual competency profile of manager No. 8 (Graph 7), in general, all competencies are at a similar level of development (1.75÷2.0 points), with the exception of the “Stress Resistance” competency (1.5 points). There are 3 “peaks” of competencies – “Result Orientation”, “Execution Management” and “Self-Organization” (all 2.0 points). Overall, this manager has a high (compared to others) average competency score. In addition, he has a fairly high score in the “Leadership” competency, which is the least developed among all competencies in the sample of managers under study. Thus, for all groups of competencies, this manager scored above the average for

the group (with the exception of participant No.4). This makes manager No.8 stand out from the rest of the group in a better way.

Figure 8. Individual competency profile of a manager under No. 11.

In graph 8 there is clearly only one peak value, which falls on the competency “Ability to work in a team” (2.25 points). At the same time, there are very low scores for such competencies as “Result Orientation” (0.5), as well as relatively low scores for the competencies “Leadership” and “Stress Resistance” (only 1.0 points each). These results significantly distinguish this manager from others for the worse.

Graph 9 shows the individual competency profile of manager No. 4, which is visually and meaningfully close to the estimated values of management competencies shown in Graph 7. In terms of core competencies, manager No. 4 has above-average ratings, which sets him apart from the entire sample for the better.

Figure 9. Individual competency profile of a manager under No. 4.

Two managers who “fall out” from the general group – Nos. 4 and 8 – have high scores in the “Leadership” competency. Manager No. 11, on the contrary, has low scores in the “Leadership”, “Result Orientation” and “Stress Resistance” competencies, but quite high scores in the “Ability to work in a team” and “Execution Management” competencies.

Visualization of the values of assessments of management competencies for managers who did not have significant connections between the assessments of these management competencies with other managers made it possible to visualize the difference in the results obtained by individual managers from the rest of the managers included in the sample under study. The authors propose to use the identified differences in assessments of management competencies to form the intellectual capital of an enterprise through training and development of management competencies in formed groups of managers and individually, which will subsequently allow managing the formation of the intellectual potential of the enterprise.

Conclusion

The results obtained during the study allow us to draw the following conclusions.

1. In the course of conducting an empirical study using the AC method, methods of qualitative and quantitative analysis, results were obtained indicating the advisability of their use for diagnosing the managerial and professional competencies of middle managers as an important component of the human capital of an enterprise. The possibility of assessing managerial and professional competencies over time gives grounds to assert that there are innovations in the dynamic approach to managing the formation of human capital in enterprises.
2. Based on the results obtained during the empirical research, the structure of managerial and professional competencies was identified. It can be relied upon when developing competency development programs for middle managers of enterprises.
3. When analyzing the correlation matrix of assessments of managerial and professional competencies of middle managers of the enterprise under study, average positive connections were identified between the competencies “Result Orientation” and “Leadership” (0.601), as well as between the competencies “Leadership” and “Execution Management” (0.574). The presence of an average negative relationship between the competencies “Stress resistance” and “Performance management” (-0.509) deserves special attention. The article substantiates possible interpretations of the presence of these connections.
4. The results of the quantitative analysis can be used as a basis for forming groups of managers for their training and subsequent development of managerial and professional competencies. The presence of connections between assessments of these competencies will allow managers to be grouped into groups with different training programs depending on their level of development. Visualization of assessments of managerial and professional competencies of managers who had no connections with assessments of the competencies of other managers in the correlation matrix made it possible to visualize the difference between their results and others, both for the better and for the worse.

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